

Helpdesk / zendesk training

June 2020

Zendesk?

- <https://telraam.zendesk.com/>

You as an agent

Elke Franchois x + Add

Mobilier21 (create) Elke Franchois Apps

Role Administrator

Groups Leuven Lubbeek Support

Alias Telraam Customer Service

Signature -

Agent + add number forwarding

Explore

Role Admin

Primary email elke.franchois@mobilier21... + add contact

Tags -

Org. + add organization

User segments -

Language Engels (Verenigde Staten) ...

Time zone (GMT+02:00) Brussels

Details -

Notes -

Created Dec 13, 2018 11:36
Updated 7 minutes ago
Last sign-in Today 09:28

+ New Ticket

Tickets (1133) Help Center (194) Security Settings Preferences

There are no apps installed in this location

Browse the Zendesk Marketplace for 600+ apps and integrations!

Browse

You as an agent

Personal preferences

- Role
- E-mail
- Signature
- Language
- Groups

Support

Submit a request

Your email address

Subject

Description

Please enter the details of your request. A member of our support staff will respond as soon as possible.

Camera position/ Road segment (optional)

You can find this on your dashboard.

Unique serial number (optional)

This can be found in the last step of your setup.

Attachments (optional)

How does a ticket come about?

- Someone sends an e-mail to support@telraam.net
- Someone fills in webform
- Someone uses the webwidget
- You forward an (helpdesk) e-mail to support@telraam.net
- Twitter

The flow of a ticket

Agent View of Tickets

- Action Needed
- SLA

The screenshot shows a ticket management interface. On the left is a sidebar with a teal background and a red arrow pointing down. The sidebar has a 'Views' section with a list of categories and their counts: 'Action needed' (11), 'Waiting for customer' (21), 'Geparkeerd' (7), 'SLA vervallen' (3), 'My tickets' (17), 'Recently updated tickets' (38), 'All onopgeloste tickets' (39), 'Social messaging - Assigned to you' (0), 'Social messaging - Unassigned' (0), 'Suspended tickets' (0), and 'Deleted tickets' (22). A blue arrow points to 'Action needed'. Below the sidebar is a table of 11 tickets under the heading 'Action needed'.

<input type="checkbox"/>	ID	Channel	Requester	Subject	Requested	Assignee	Next SLA breach
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1736	Mail	Hendrik De Langhe	Re: Uw Telraam camera lijkt geen gegevens meer door te sturen	Yesterday 13:39	Elke Franchois	3d
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1702	Web form	Psykle1	Camera Angle	Jun 07	-	3d
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1723	Mail	luc@tilkin.eu	Re: Uw Telraam camera lijkt geen gegevens meer door te sturen	Thursday 16:54	-	3d
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1119	Web form	Johan Bertrands	winkelstraat diestsestraat	Feb 14	Elke Franchois	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1493	Mail	Elke Franchois	Re: een telraam	Apr 30	-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1525	Web form	Peter Hoste	Telraam stokerijstraat Wijnegem	May 01	-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1542	Web form	Baetensj	geen verbinding met wifi	May 05	-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1571	Closed ticket	Paul Annys	Re: Uw Telraam camera lijkt geen gegevens meer door te sturen	May 11	Elke Franchois	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1604	Mail	Jos ROBERT	Twee vragen	May 18	Elke Franchois	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1613	Closed ticket	Jeroen Steeman	RE: Re: Telraam valt (random) uit	May 20	Elke Franchois	
<input type="checkbox"/>	#1620	Closed ticket	Jeroen	RE: Re: Telraam valt (random) uit	May 22	-	

Set up Zendesk in Telraam

- Views tickets → Action needed
- Assigned tickets (Based on E-mail of client and Group of agent)
- SLA planning
- Follow up tickets

Ticket status

- Standard
- Waiting for customer
- Parked

How to work with a ticket

- Answer
 - Look for user information in dashboard
 - Find FAQ article via knowledge centre 🔍
 - Ask internal (Elke and/or Carl) – assign to Carl, make internal note
 - Ask external (eg send to Kris - side conversation) – add ticket info to e-mail
- Assign status
 - Open
 - Pending
 - Parked
 - Solved

User information in Zendesk

- Name
- Email
- Address
- Status Telraam
- Network (as tag)
- Other tickets

TEST Ticket

- [Create ticket](#)
- Reply on ticket

Helpdesk and platform

Organisatie (maken)

Mieke Vandermotte

Medewerker

[ik pak dit op](#)

Support/Carl Van Poyer

Volgers

[volgen](#)

agenten zoeken

Tags

kessel-lo

Type

Vraag

Prioriteit

Normaal

Camera positie / Wegsegment

Uniek serienummer

Dublin ▾

Dashboard

Camera's

Users

Membership

Network Settings

Admin Members

Guide

Add ▾

Guide admin

TELRAAM

Telraam Customer Service ▾

English (US) ▾

🔍 Search

Telraam and Privacy?

General questions about Telraam

What is Telraam, what does Telraam count, how can I take part...?

Telraam installation

You can find an answer to your installation questions here.

My Telraam is in place, now what?

Viewing data, informing neighbours...

WeCount

WeCount is an European project that enables citizens to initiate a policy-making process with fully automated measure...

 WECOUNT

Add ▾

Edit article

Guide admin

Telraam Helpcenter > General questions about Telraam

Search

Articles in this section

What is Telraam?

What do I need to set up Telraam in my window?

What exactly does Telraam count?

Why and when does Telraam not count?

How do I count?

Is Telraam difficult to

What is Telraam?

3 months ago · Updated

Follow

The project started in March 2019 with a pilot study in Kessel-Lo. There, 100 residents carried out their own traffic counts using a specially developed low-cost sensor, Telraam, from their windows.

Frequently Asked Questions – Articles most referred to

- No data yet – Wifi
<https://telraam.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/360025950831-I-can-t-get-my-Telraam-to-connect-to-Wi-Fi->
- & <https://telraam.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/360026050091-No-data-is-coming-from-my-Telraam-yet>
- Suddenly no more data
<https://telraam.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/360028290252-Data-from-my-Telraam-suddenly-stops-coming-through>
- Classification / calibration/ Data is wrong
<https://telraam.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/360035237672-Telraam-calibration-and-the-ratio-auto-large-vehicles>
- Unstable connection - <https://telraam.zendesk.com/hc/en-us/articles/360050859691-The-connection-between-my-Telraam-and-the-wifi-is-sometimes-lost->

Contact

Contact

No helpdesk question?
Asking for information?

→@telraam.net

madrid@telraam.net

ljubljana@telraam.net

Cardiff@telraam.net

Dublin@telraam.net

leuven@telraam.net

....

WWW.WE-COUNT.NET

IDEAS
FOR
CHANGE

Univerza v Ljubljani

MOBIEL21
ZET MENSEN IN BEWEGING